

The Media (Series/Films) & Their Influence on Young People's Views of Cannabis's Adverse Effects

Bianka Sarkozi

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8353255 | ISSN: 2977-1676

The Journal of
Crime & Justice
Dissertations

About: The “Journal of Crime & Justice Dissertations” (JCJD) is an online platform for student dissertations. The JCJD is a London Metropolitan University [Crime Lab project](#) which was established in 2023.

The JCJD does not make use of a peer-review process as is typical with standard academic journals. Rather the JCJD serves primarily as a platform to showcase high-achieving student dissertations that relate to the concepts of social justice and social harm. All dissertations are sourced from reputable universities and all dissertations have received a 1st class grade. The JCJD makes use of an inspection process but this is only to ensure that the minimum requirements of the platform are upheld (it is not a peer-review process). JCJD publications should be read in this context, the publications are students' work and should not be used in the same manner as rigorously peer-reviewed content. For a full disclaimer regarding the JCJD and for more details regarding the inspection process for dissertations, please visit the website journalcjd.org.

Director (Editor in Chief): Shaun S. Yates.

Executive Committee: Ellada Larionidou, James Alexander, Jade Benn, Gordana Uzelac, Eden Zaidner, Denise Morrison, Isifu Mwase.

Address: London Metropolitan University, 166-220 Holloway Road, London, N7 8DB.

www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8353255>

© 2023 by The Journal of Crime & Justice Dissertations (JCJD).

Abstract

This research has aimed to understand the influence of films and series on the perception of young people (aged 18-25) regarding the negative effects of cannabis. To achieve this objective, this study employed a quantitative approach, specifically using an online survey with 63 participants. Respondents were asked about their views on how the media portrays cannabis use, whether it influences their generation, and if individuals are aware of the harmful effects of cannabis, among other questions. A key finding of this dissertation is that depictions of cannabis in the media (series and movies) is on the rise. Moreover, series and movies seem to significantly influence young people, making them more likely to experiment with substances such as cannabis. Finally, this dissertation argues that the media presents an inaccurate representation of the harms associated with cannabis use.

Contents Page

Abstract.....	1
Contents Page	2
Chapter 1: Introduction	3
Chapter 2: Literature Review.....	6
Chapter 3: Methodology.....	11
Chapter 4: Findings.....	14
Chapter 5: Conclusion.....	23
References	26

Chapter 1: Introduction

This dissertation aims to discuss how young individuals (aged between 18 and 25) may be influenced by the media, particularly films and series, concerning the adverse effects of cannabis use. This study will concentrate on how the media affects people's perceptions, ideas, and beliefs about cannabis usage. It will also highlight how shows and movies educate young people about cannabis's harmful effects.

To have a better understanding of the subject, it is essential to first define a few terms. 'Drug abuse' is defined as any use of drugs for non-medical purposes, almost always for altering consciousness. Drug abuse denotes substances that change the mental or physical state of a person, and that may be used repeatedly for that effect leading to abnormality.

It is also necessary to know what cannabis is and how/why it can affect our behaviour/mood. Cannabis is a substance, "the most widely grown illegalised plant, covering 159" (Farber, 2021 p92). This substance is made from the herbaceous plant *Cannabis sativa*, which thrives in various parts of the world (Farber, 2021). Cannabis had previously been incorrectly labelled as a narcotic, a sedative, and, most lately, a hallucinogen (Dewey, 1986). Even though cannabinoids have stimulating, sedative, and hallucinogenic effects (Adams & Martin, 1996), cannabinoids actually belong to a medicinal class of chemicals known as: terpenophenolic secondary metabolites (Adams & Martin, 1996). Cannabis acts on the cannabinoid receptors in the brain, unlike other hallucinogenic substances (Dewey, 1986). Many studies on cannabinoids have been motivated by the aim of discovering the molecular mechanism that underlies the euphoric impact that cannabis produces (Martin, 1986).

Presently, movies are a typical kind of mass communication. In the previous three to four decades, they have evolved from being merely unnecessary instruments for fun to something more substantial. Viewers are more influenced by films because they can connect emotionally to the performers as well as the actions and are impacted by the way the actors represent these figures. Our everyday routine may be impacted by television, they have an influence on how individuals dress, what they eat, and how they communicate (Ferla, 2010). Several studies (for example see Roberts et al., 1999; Gerbner et al., 2002) have found that recent movies and television shows include greater violence and drug usage than they did in the past. These studies (Ferla, 2010; Roberts et al., 1999; Gerbner et al., 2002) show that the media is at least partly responsible for the rising number of young people suffering from

substance use disorders. Although media is a part of our daily lives, is it beneficial to our mental health? Does the media give viewers a sufficient model to emulate? How much do individuals actually succumb to the harmful impacts of the movies/series? This dissertation will examine the persuasive effects of media depicting cannabis usage, including movies and series.

The study also investigates how young people view these materials and attempts to ascertain how much material affects young individuals' conduct. This project aims to examine how censoring in contemporary films affects young people's social and cognitive development. The study concludes by considering social responsibility and whether film stars and the entertainment industry as a whole are responsible for upholding stricter censorship norms or if they are solely creating works of art for the medium and should not be held responsible for what they portray in the media. According to content studies, depictions of illegal drugs appear in 22% of films (Roberts et al., 1999), and they are presented 0.60 times per hour on average. According to studies, representations of drug use on prime-time broadcast increased "from 0.22 times per hour in the 1970s to 0.83 and 0.53 times per hour in the 1980s and 1990s, respectively", (Gerbner & Ozyegin, 1997, p130; FernandezCollado et al., 1978). In addition to being presented quite frequently, stereotypes also exist regarding users of illegal drugs and the effects of drug abuse (Gerbner & Ozyegin, 1997). Secondly, substance users are frequently presented as criminals in the media instead of as individuals with a manageable addiction (Gerbner & Ozyegin, 1997).

Additionally, young characters, particularly in fictional programs, are linked to substance abuse (Winick & Winick, 1976). In their analysis of the incidence of illicit substance use on TV, Judith Long et al. (2002) discovered that an actor's likelihood of using drugs is more likely if they are under 35 than when the character is over 35. Seventy-Four per cent of cannabis-related incidents in films included people between the ages of 19 and 25, according to Hasantha Gunasekera et al. (2005). As such, young individuals are represented in the media as more likely to use illicit substances than older people.

Moreover, adolescents who use drugs are adversely characterised (Hasantha Gunasekera et al., 2005). As a global problem, substance abuse is commonly discussed in newscasts and is becoming a crucial subject in prime-time broadcasts and films (Solowij, 1998). This dissertation will also look into how much people are aware of the harmful effects of substance misuse, as well as how accurately the media presents this vital topic. Two of the most important topics for this project are addiction and substance abuse. In addition, studies on crimes involving substance abuse and the effects of the media will be included. Because addiction and the effects of media share many similarities with the topic of

psychological well-being, some mental health-related themes will also play an essential role in this research (Lindholm, 2015).

Chapter 2: Literature Review

There are many theories that explain the relationship between drug abuse, young people and the media. The first theory that needs to be mentioned is Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) conducted by Bandura (1986). This theory discusses how an "individual's knowledge acquisition can be directly related to observing others within the context of social interactions, experiences, and outside media influences", (Bandura, 1986, p. 63). Bandura's social cognitive theory of human functioning emphasises the critical importance of self-belief in human cognition, motivation, and behaviour. The self-system that allows people to have some degree of control regarding their ideas, emotions, and behaviours is highlighted by social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1986). In order to examine the factors and psychosocial systems through which interaction impacts individual thoughts and behaviour, SCT offers a solid theoretical foundation (Bandura, 2001). SCT looks into the psychosocial factors that influence learning, assimilation, and the social networks that propagate and maintain unique behavioural patterns (Ju et al., 2022). Structural interconnectivity provides possible distribution pathways; sociocognitive variables essentially control what disperses across those networks (Merchant, 2013, p.6). According to triadic reciprocal causation which is "based on the recognition that autonomous learning and self-directed learning involve a "reciprocity of interaction between the learner, his or her learning behaviours, and the environment (Guglielmino, 2012 p2); SCT explains psychosocial functioning (Bandura, 1986). In this transactional perspective on one's personality and society, individual characteristics in the way that are cognitive, social, and biological events, behavioural tendencies, and environmental factors all work as interacting determinants that impact each other "bidirectionally" (Merchant, 2013, p.6). To summarise the above concept, "observational learning and retention are" (Merchant, 2013, p6) crucial in determining how individuals behave. This comprises movie-related material.

To investigate whether films had any social-psychological consequences, Leyens and Camino (1975) looked at how violence in films affected individuals to behave aggressively. In their study, one group of participants saw violent and aggressive films, whereas the other group of participants solely watched neutral, non-violence movies. The group exposed to violent content showed an apparent rise in verbal and physical hostility (Leyens and Camino, 1975). The claim that movie content may have an impact on people's conduct is therefore supported by SCT. Yet, others have shown that peer pressure and familial influences have a more significant influence on drinking behaviour than movie plots (Cin et al. 2009).

Whilst useful, SCT has some limitations. The theory assumes that an individual will change with the environment (Nabi & Clark, 2008). It is debatable how much these factors affect how people behave in daily life and if one is more significant than the other. Additionally, the strategy places a lot of attention on learning processes while downplaying hormonal and physiological traits that could affect behaviour despite understanding or expectations (Nabi & Clark, 2008). The notion needs to put more focus on motive or emotion, other than using prior information. These factors should be given more thought. It can also be difficult to fully operationalise the theory because it has so many ramifications (Nabi & Clark, 2008).

Although Cin et al.'s (2009) research suggests that films may not always be the primary element affecting young people's decisions, it nonetheless recognises their influence and contribution to shaping behaviour. Relatedly, Shapiro (2002) carried out a study of how substance usage, mainly cocaine use, has been portrayed in movies from World War I until 2002. Again, the images varied from a sombre situation to more humorous ones. This analysis is crucial because it shows how substance use has been portrayed and how it has evolved in relation to generational differences and movie types. During World War II, portrayals of substance use often for comic effect or it referred to someone's mental health (see "comic drunk" in Room, 2015, p3). Nevertheless, both during and following the 1960s, substance issues, addictions, and recovery became the focus of several films (Shapiro, 2002). Once again, the emphasis shifted as substance usage was linked to sex and violence in the 1980s and 1990s. This report provides a definitive account of the variables that affected how drug use was portrayed and how it was affected by viewers' preferences at that period. Nevertheless, Shapiro (2002) argues that there is a limitation as films are not promoting substance use on purpose; instead, they only represent actual life and are related to the style of the movie.

Another theory that is relevant to this project is the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM). The elaboration likelihood model (ELM), invented by psychologists Richard E. Petty and John Cacioppo in the 1980s, looks at how and why individuals make choices. The fundamental tenet of ELM is that mindsets have influential characteristics because they direct our behaviour while making decisions (Praditomo, 2022). An individual's attitudes are their tendencies or viewpoints towards anything, and they are influenced by a variety of factors (Praditomo, 2022). The idea aims to discover the elements that influence people to choose a specific path of action or exhibit a particular behaviour (Petty, 1986). ELM is known as a dual-process model since it provides two possibilities for attitude construction and change: high involvement or core mode; low interest or peripheral mode. (Petty, 1986). The length of the elaboration process is determined by the level of engagement. Peripheral persuasion is a cognitive

"shortcut" that leads people to accept or reject a response based on irrelevant cues rather than properly evaluating the issue. (Praditomo, 2022, p.211). The mechanism through which external factors have an impact on the decision-making procedure is referred to as the peripheral route. Aggression, substance use, and unprotected sex are frequent film themes that could have an impact on viewers, particularly younger viewers (Praditomo, 2022), which is the reason why it is relevant to this project. This model, however, has limitations, and the concept clearly states that it depends on the message elaboration: "the extent to which people think consciously about a message" (Loman et al, 2019). It does not indicate when to utilise a specific method of persuasion (Sridharan, 2021). Moreover, the approach is predicated on the idea that built cognition would be more profound and much more challenging to change, which can be seen as a critique rather than a drawback (Sridharan, 2021).

Hunt et al. (2011) examined the relationship between young individual being exposed to substance usage in movies and their personal substance usage. The experiment, which tracked children's growth into adulthood, was carried out in Scotland. From the age of 11, these teenagers were watched for periods of two years as they went about their film habits. Lastly, they were examined at age 19 to see if there was a connection between their film-watching and substance abuse. These kids began watching movies with substances when they were 11 years old. The scientists discovered that one-third of these young individuals were categorised as 'heavy drinkers' and almost 50% were 'binge drinkers' based on their previous week's consumption. (Merchant, 2013. p.19-20). Over 50% claimed to have ever used cannabis, and 13% admitted to taking at least one of the "hard" substances mentioned. The results show that movies that the individuals viewed from childhood significantly had impacts on their conduct as adults because the majority of them reported significant alcohol use weekly as well as use of cannabis and other dangerous substances (Hunt et al., 2011). Investigators were able to verify that films efficiently impact youngsters and that witnessing substance usage on television might have an adverse impact on them, according to this eight-year longitudinal study. The results of this study, which was carried out in Scotland but had universal ramifications, demonstrate that there is a global problem with regard to how films affect people (Hunt et al., 2011).

The worldwide scope of this problem is also demonstrated by the German research of Hanewinkel (2008). Hanewinkel (2008) concentrated on parental controls over children's viewing of films with youth tobacco and alcohol use. This research aimed to find out whether youngsters who said their parents forbade them from seeing films about teen tobacco and alcohol use had a lower likelihood of ever doing it themselves. The emphasis was on films with the limitation "FSK-16," which denotes films that are only appropriate for viewers who are at least 16 years old. The caregivers and the youngsters

were divided into the following categories: the kids whose parents did not restrict them, the youngsters whose parents did not let them access the "FSK-16" films, the children who occasionally had access, and the kids whose parents sometimes let them watch these movies. The findings revealed, "After adjusting for variables, parental movie restriction had a substantial impact on each substance use outcome measure." FSK-16 limits were linked to lower viewing of all movie genres, especially FSK-16/18 films. They were also linked to significantly lower exposure to cigarette and alcohol use in movies, which suggests a mediating mechanism for the association." (Hanewinkel, et. al., 2008, p 1728) The highest number of drug and alcohol use was seen in youngsters with no parental limitations, while the lowest percentage was seen in kids whose guardians forbade them from watching "FSK-16" movies. The two other groups of kids had findings that were quite comparable and were less inclined to engage with substances such as alcohol and drugs than kids who routinely viewed movies with adult content. The findings demonstrate a strong link between parental censoring and a lower likelihood of substance abuse later (Hanewinkel et al., 2008). This analysis was intriguing since it showed how parental censoring influenced kids' decisions to abstain from substance usage (Hanewinkel et al., 2008).

An investigation into drug use in Brazilian films from 2000 to 2008 was conducted in by Castaldelli-Maia et al. (2013) using a sample of fifty films. The researchers discovered that scenes demonstrate drug usage nearly equivalent to what occurs in the community, mainly alcohol, cannabis and inhalants (Castadelli et al., 2013). Nevertheless, they also discovered that in comparison to actual substance use in films, cocaine use was overexposed, and tranquiliser use was underexposed. It also indicates that, while some films are making progress in a favourable way showing less substance use and violence there are still occasions where the subject matter is presented and therefore makes negative influence (Castadelli et al., 2013).

The next theory that applies to this topic is the cultivation theory, which is grounded in the investigation of television media. According to Cultivation Theory, individuals have a greater tendency to embrace the social reality depicted in films if they spend more extended time immersed in the entertainment of tv or, in this situation, films and series (Cohen & Weimann, 2000). In accordance with the theory's concept, viewing a lot of media depicting substance use may cause viewers to associate those behaviours with reality and think that using substances is expected behaviour (Cohen & Weimann, 2000).

Furthermore, studies discovered that when data dramatisation increases, complex thinking decreases, leading to more radical conclusions (Brosius, 1996). According to these findings, Charles Aust and Dolf Zillmann (1996) found that even if given objective, truthful evidence, individuals still have a tendency

to accept abnormal depictions of events when they are given enough emotional impact. It indicates that viewers' emotions can be easily affected by what they see in films/series, and as a result, they are more likely to believe and retain adverse and incorrect information. Media can benefit from this phenomenon; for example, if we look into advertising, we can observe that many commercials involve emotional scenes which have a greater influence on viewers and make them more inclined to purchase the product that has been advertised (Aust and Zillmann, 1996).

Estimates of youngsters' substance usage rise as a result of increased television exposure (Aust & Zillmann, 1996). Furthermore, it is believed that educational attainment has an impact on how sophisticated a person's mind is (Sotirovic, 2001). An individual's thoughts will often be more sophisticated with more schooling, which can mean a greater tendency not to engage with drug abuse.

The European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction (EMCDDA) gathers, examines, and publishes experimental data on drug-related concerns and presents a fact-based analysis of the drug abuse phenomenon. Young men had the highest prevalence of illicit drug usage (15-34 years old). The rising use of synthetic cannabinoids (SCs) across the globe has led to a rise in unforeseen problems and illnesses. Many medical professionals are ignorant of the frequency, intensity, and possible hazards of physical and psychological symptoms in addition to the consumption of SCs (EMCDDA, 2023).

Studies of substance users have generally focused on issues that are either personal to the consumer or societal in nature (Sulkunen, 2002). The semiotic approach of the 1980s focused on the social aspects of substance usage, such as how various substances are connected to ideas, interpretations, and perceptions among various social classes (Sulkunen, 2002). According to this paradigm, the significance of drugs takes precedence over the earlier emphasis on the issues and risks associated with substance use which means it became more important to societies worldwide to focus more on the addicts and addiction instead of the substances itself (Hellum, 2010). Much ethnographic research was undertaken in the 1990s, mainly among young males, as a consequence of the semiotic turn in the mid-1990s (Lalander, 2001). In order to comprehend illegal substance usage amongst youngsters, concepts like identity, the meaning of substances, and 'social' become crucial. Throughout this paradigm, different substances and sensations of intoxication were investigated in relation to other phenomena in the general public, like isolation from society, starvation, homelessness, destitution, as well as other economic concerns (Hellum, 2010).

Chapter 3: Methodology

The information related to this investigation was gathered and analysed using quantitative approaches. Data from numerous studies on this topic indicate that films and television shows indeed have an effect on young people. The same conclusion was made in the project's online survey as well (Hanewinkel et al., 2008). Theorists of social cognition and persuasion confirm that viewers are most probably influenced by movies (Shapiro, 2002). This suggests that watching films with actors who use illicit substances excessively will encourage youngsters to engage in unhealthy habits. Once these youngsters begin at an early age, it is quite difficult to eradicate these addictions (Hunt et al., 2011).

This report concentrated on how stereotypes and cultivation, as well as cognition and persuasion, influence young people's opinions on cannabis use and the possibility that young individuals exposed to media with cannabis-related protagonists will also engage in this harmful activity. It aims to determine the impact of media that encourages youngsters to participate in harmful habits but fails to portray the adverse impacts of doing so, as well as how this could influence their personality (Nalkur et al., 2010). The project examines the subject and provides research-related questions, with a particular emphasis on whether parental and maybe governmental control might lessen youth access to substance usage.

This research investigated whether young viewers are conscious of this issue or have been impacted in any way by these substances in movies. From the younger generation's viewpoint, this will enable us to understand better how and why film industries advertise films that include substance use to children. Previous studies on the subject were primarily conducted from a survey of juvenile behaviour rather than from the youths' own perceptions of the factors that contribute to illicit substance use (Nalkur et al., 2010).

The quantitative research method of a questionnaire has been chosen to investigate the responses to the research questions. An online survey and a Google form have been made, and information has been shared about it with friends, acquaintances, classmates, and organisations that help undergraduate students with their studies (these groups mentioned above were mainly assessed through Facebook). Likert scales were used in the online survey for most of the questions, and respondents could select from five categories: strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neither agree nor disagree (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5). Applying an analytical approach made it possible to gain a greater understanding of

the research as a whole by dissecting complex processes into their component elements. In this particular case, Excel formulas and Google form graphics were used to assess the data.

Individuals were contacted in the manner outlined in the plan through a variety of methods, including direct emails and social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat), asking whether they would be willing to take part in this project. Using this methodology has a number of benefits and disadvantages. The method for collecting observable data to investigate a research topic through quantitative, analytical, or mathematical methods is known as quantitative data analysis. It is frequently thought to be more reliable or effective than qualitative research. The focus of quantitative research is on quantifiable connections. It can be examined and verified. In order to do quantitative research, thorough experimental planning and the capacity for universal testing and outcome replication are essential. As a result, the information the researcher collects is more trustworthy and less subject to debate. The structured style has a benefit in that it offers more comprehensive samples of quantitative data that can be directly measured and relied upon (Byman, 2008). The findings that can be obtained from collecting quantitative data can help decide which independent analyses to conduct.

The quantitative approach also has the benefit of being relatively inexpensive and inexpensive. It is representative and may be generalisable if the sampling has little to no limitation (Byman,2008). For all of these, the quantitative methodology has disadvantages as well. Analysts may miss more significant aspects and connections as a result of quantitative research's potential limitations in its pursuit of specific statistical associations. There is a potential risk of overlooking unexpected or broad-based data that could improve the investigation if the researcher only concentrates on the numbers. Data analysis can be modified to produce a subjective outcome, whether this is done on an intended or unintentional basis or as a consequence of the investigators' prejudice. The findings that follow can only be appropriately evaluated if the background of the figures is fully provided or if they were collected in an inconsistent or deceptive manner. It may not give rich, in-depth data like interviews.

The anonymity and confidentiality of this methodology were guaranteed because it did not ask for any personal data other than age, sex, and ethnicity. This project primarily aimed towards the younger generations (age 18-25) because they are more adaptable to new technology, more open-minded, and access media more regularly than people from older generations (Oda Faremo Lindholm, 2015). The goal of this research was to evaluate a wide range of viewpoints. As an undergraduate research project, the survey could not include questions regarding someone's mental state and whether they are engaging in any substance use or if they had a criminal offence. Also, an undergraduate study requires participants to be at least 18 years old in order to participate. The investigation complied with the Data

Protection Act of 2018, and participants were treated with respect. Protecting the respondents' anonymity, safety, and confidentiality is crucial. The dissertation project did not demand any personal information from anyone who chooses to participate besides age, sex and ethnicity, as it was guaranteed. Some people may find this survey to be distressing psychologically or emotionally. A preview of the study topic has been created and shared with the respondents previously as an introduction to prevent any distress and to avoid misinterpretation. As a result, it made it clear to the people who were being targeted what was being researched and why a particular approach was chosen.

Chapter 4: Findings

As it has been mentioned, a quantitative research method was chosen for conducting this research. A questionnaire was conducted in order to analyse data. There were 62 individuals who participated altogether. Most of the respondents were aged 18-21 (n=31), and the respondents were primarily females (n=39); as for ethnicity, the vast majority were white (n=55). The questions focused on serials & films, and how cannabis appears in the media, also what effects cannabis has on the youth. Among the 62 participants, 61 said that they watch serials and films regularly. As the online survey focused on people between 18-25, data were analysed according to this manner. Altogether there were 49 young individuals whose answers were analysed.

The first two questions (Chart 1, Chart 2) intended to find out whether the participants think that in the past five years, there have been more scenes, including cannabis usage or dealing with cannabis. According to 48 respondents, 28 (58.3%) (strongly agree: n=10, 20.8%; agree: n=18, 37.5%) believe that in the past five years, there have been more scenes, including dealing with cannabis. Moreover, 31 participants (64.6%) (strongly agree: n=10, 20.8%; agree: n=21, 43.8%) agreed that in the past five years, more scenes involved cannabis usage. As previous studies mentioned earlier in the project (Roberts et al., 1999; Gerbner & Ozyegin, 1997) suggest, there is an increasing pattern in the representation of illicit substances in the media. Furthermore, Hasantha Gunasekera et al. (2005) determined that cannabis in television is mostly (74% of cannabis-related incidents) used by people aged 19-25. As such, young individuals are represented in media portrayals as being more likely to use illicit substances than adults or older adults (Hasantha-Gunasekera et al., 2005).

The respondents of the survey were also asked (Chart 3) if they agree with the fact that Hasantha-Gunesakera et al. (2015) suggest that there are more young actors (age 18-25) in the scenes in serials and movies who participate in cannabis use (as their roles). 32 individuals (66.7%) agreed (agree: n=20, 41.7%, strongly agreed: n=12, 25%).

Fig. 1 graph to show how strongly participants agreed or disagreed with the following statement: In the past 5 years there are more scenes in series/films that include dealing with cannabis.

Fig. 2 graph to show how strongly participants agreed or disagreed with the following statement: In the past 5 years there are ore scenes in film/series including cannabis use.

Fig. 3 graph to show how strongly participants agreed or disagreed with the following statement: In the past 5 years there are more young actors (age 18-25) in the scenes in series/film who participate in cannabis use (as their roles).

It has been mentioned before in an eight-year longitudinal study conducted by Hunt et al. (2011) that films and series quickly impact young individuals and that witnessing substance usage on television might have an adverse impact on them, according to this study. The results of this study, which was carried out in Scotland but had universal ramifications, demonstrate that there is a global problem concerning how films affect people (Hunt et al, 2011). Although much research aimed to investigate the relationship between television and its adverse influence on viewers, there are still individuals who confidently state that films and series do not have a negative influence on them. In the quantitative research that was chosen for this dissertation among 48 respondents, the question regarding (Chart 4) whether they think scenes in series/films that include cannabis use have a negative influence on their generation was one of the most divisive questions in the questionnaire. There was a similar percentage to the 'neither agree nor disagree' (n=10; 20.8%) and the 'strongly agree' (n=10; 20.8%) options. There was no significant difference between the options: 'disagree' (n=9; 18.8%) and 'agree' (n=10, 20,8%). Although the responses were divisive, there was a noticeable difference: individuals were 22.9% more likely to agree on this question than disagree. There was an additional comment in the survey which is related to this question; the participant said: "I do not think these films make the young individuals use drugs because the movie/series/.. watching is a relatively short time, and they show a very different situation so that the children will not relate their life because of the differences. The use of these substances is more likely to come from the closest friendships or school, and the reason is curiosity or desolation." Many studies, for example, a longitudinal study conducted by Parker et al. (2002.), analysed whether youngsters have easy access to cannabis, among others. This research also

mentioned that the media have a crucial influence on young individuals. They are more likely to try cannabis if they watch films and series that include cannabis usage (Parker et al., 2002). This study and the respondent's comments are related to the next question (Chart 5) of the survey, which was to find out whether participants think that scenes in series/films, including cannabis use, may influence their generation to try these substances.

Fig. 4 graph to show how strongly participants agreed or disagreed with the following statement: I think scenes in series/films that include cannabis use have a negative influence on my generation.

Fig. 5 graph to show how strongly participants agreed or disagreed with the following statement: I think that scenes in series/films including cannabis use may influence my generation to try these substances.

As the reader can see from the results (Chart 5), there is a considerable difference between participants who agreed (agree n=19, 39.6%; strongly agree n=18, 37.5%) and those who did not (disagree n=1, 2.1%; strongly disagree n=3 6.3%). However, there is evidence that films and series have a harmful effect on youngsters. There were also two additional comments in the questionnaire that stated that trying cannabis and becoming addicted is more related to the influence of peers rather than the media:

1. I believe that youngsters mostly try substances because of the influence of their peers. They desire to fit in, and that is why they might be becoming addicts.
2. Using cannabis or drugs does not really depend on series/serials/films; it is all about your company and their habits. These activities in series/serials/films might teach you how to handle these situations and how to keep your boundaries.

According to recent research by Caballero et al. (2023), the respondent's statement is somewhat true. Youngsters might try cannabis because they would like to fit in. Also, they believe that if they are the only one in their friend group who does not use cannabis, they would be ostracised and stigmatised (Caballero et al., 2003). They are the most vulnerable generation when it comes to stigmatisation and labelling; For this particular reason, youngsters have more tendency to try illicit substances than any other generations (Caballero et al., 2023). There were questions in the survey which aimed to find out what are the participants' opinions on drug-prevention methods; they were asked how schools, parents and the media can educate young individuals on cannabis use and to what extent respondents think that educational facilities, guardians and the media inform youngsters about the adverse effect of cannabis. There was a noticeable difference regarding the question of whether respondents think that series/films are helpful tools to prevent their generations from cannabis use (Chart 6). Only 14.6% (n=7) of the participants agreed.

Fig. 6 graph to show how strongly participants agreed or disagreed with the following statement: I think that series/films are helpful tools in preventing my generation from cannabis use.

It has already been mentioned that cannabis usage in films and series has a crucial impact on young individuals (Fernández-Collado et al., 1978); as in the media, cannabis usage is often broadcasted positively, it becomes evident that movies and serials might not be the best means to prevent youngsters from cannabis usage. According to Newcomb and Bentler (1989), media almost popularise illegal substance usage, as characters in television are often perceived as humorous, powerful, popular and hardly ever seen as serious addicts or criminals. So the reader already has some evidence that the media is not an appropriate means to prevent young people from cannabis usage, but where can young people access reliable information about substance usage? There were two questions in the questionnaire asking participants whether they think schools and parents can educate young individuals about the harmful effect of cannabis. Respondents were more likely to believe that parents and caregivers can educate youngsters more appropriately (50%) about the adverse effect of drugs than schools (27.1%). 22.9% more people agreed that parental education is more effective. Although respondents were more likely to believe that parental education about the harmful effects of cannabis use is more efficient, in another question, the results were interestingly controversial; (Chart 7); the majority of participants (strongly disagree: n=10, 20.8%; disagree: n=14; 29.2%) thought that parents/caregivers are not aware that their children might use cannabis. O'Loughlin et al. (2019) confirmed this idea in their research. They found out that adolescents who had never used cannabis before were 1.8 times more likely to start using cannabis during high school if their guardians were also users, among others. Moreover, they also mentioned that the majority of parents are hardly ever aware of their children's cannabis usage (Kokotovič et al., 2022).

Fig. 7 graph to show how strongly participants agreed or disagreed with the following statement: I think that parents/caregivers are aware that their children might use cannabis.

All the previous questions in the survey referred to cannabis usage. However, there was a particular question (Chart 8) which intended to find out if participants think people are aware of the harmful effect of drugs. Although the results suggest that individuals are aware of the adverse effects (altogether, 39.6% agreed, and only 27.1% disagreed), there was one participant who had an additional comment mentioning: "I think people are only aware of the harmful effect of drugs in general. They only know that it is bad for their health, but they do not really know the actual adverse effects. That is why more and more people become addicts." According to Wurcel et al. (2015), the respondent statement is partially accurate. Using illegal drugs can lead to a variety of medical issues (Wurcel et al., 2015). New symptoms connected with illegal drug use may look like infections as their availability, synthesis, and popularity change over time. Many of those symptoms correspond to anticipated pharmacological side effects, while others are consequences of drug interactions with adulterants or from the way the pharmaceuticals were taken (Wurcel et al., 2015). Their research also mentioned a similar approach to what the respondent comment stated; individuals are generally aware that using illicit substances is harmful to one's health, but the profound effects are often unrecognisable and glossed over (Wurcel et al., 2015). Very often, people are misled by the media and by their peers. Genuine, reliable information hardly ever reaches individuals, which is why they naively believe they are aware of the harmful effect of drugs (Selvaggi et al.,2017).

Fig. 8 graph to show how strongly participants agreed or disagreed with the following statement: I think that people are aware of the harmful effect of drugs.

This research had some limitations. The respondents were primarily close acquaintances living in one particular country, and there were only 63 participants; for this reason, the data might not be generalisable to the whole population. There might be significant differences among different cultures and socialities. As the majority of the respondents live in the same environment, they are more likely to have similar opinions and perceptions on this research topic. The usage of illicit substances varies widely across cultures and countries, and reliable data can be challenging to obtain due to the illegal nature of the drug in many places. However, according to the United Nations World Drug Report 2021, the countries with the highest rates of cannabis use among the general population are Canada - 15.5% of the population aged 15-64 reported using cannabis in the past year. In the United States of America - 15.3% of the population aged 15-64 reported using cannabis in the past year, and in Nigeria - 14.3% of the population aged 15-64 reported using cannabis in the past year (United Nations World Drug Report, 2021).

On the other hand, some countries have meagre rates of cannabis use. According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime's World Drug Report 2021, countries in Central and Southeast Asia tend to have lower levels of cannabis use compared to other regions. Moreover, the above-mentioned report states that the prevalence of cannabis use in Afghanistan, Cambodia, and Myanmar is relatively low compared to the global average. In many Middle Eastern countries, the use of cannabis is prohibited by law and carries severe penalties. However, due to the illicit nature of the drug, it cannot be easy to obtain reliable statistics on usage rates in these countries. It is important to note that the legality of

cannabis can vary widely from country to country and even within countries and that illicit drug use is often driven by complex socio-economic factors (United Nations, 2021). Concerning this report, 7.60% of the population in the United Kingdom reported using cannabis in 2021.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

To sum up, everything that has been stated before, the project aimed to discuss how young individuals between the ages of 18 and 25 may be influenced by media, particularly by films and series, with regard to the negative effects of cannabis use. This research had the intent to find out how the media affects people's perceptions, ideas, and beliefs about cannabis usage. Moreover, it also highlighted how shows and movies educate young people about cannabis' negative effects. This project included related theories like the Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura. This theory discusses how an "individual's knowledge acquisition can be directly related to observing others within the context of social interactions, experiences, and outside media influences." (Bandura, 1986. P. 63). The Elaboration likelihood model which was invented by psychologists Richard E. Petty and John Cacioppo in the 1980s, looking at how and why individuals make choices, has also been mentioned. The reader also came across the cultivation theory, which is grounded in the investigation of television media. According to Cultivation Theory, individuals have a greater tendency to embrace the social reality depicted in films if they spend longer time immersed in the entertainment of tv or, in this situation, films and series (Cohen & Weimann, 2000). It was related to the research topic as, in accordance with the theory's concept, viewing a lot of media depicting substance use may cause viewers to associate those behaviours with reality and think that using substances is normal behaviour (Cohen & Weimann, 2000). Hasantha- Gunasekara et al. (2005) conducted research where they found interesting results; Seventy-Four per cent of cannabis-related incidents in films included people between the ages of 19 and 25. As such, young individuals are represented in media portrayals as being more likely to use illicit substances than adults or older adults. Moreover, adolescents who use drugs are adversely characterised (Hasantha Gunasekera et al., 2005).

As a global problem, substance abuse is commonly discussed in newscasts and is becoming a crucial expanding subject in prime-time broadcasts and films (Solowij, 1998). Today's entertainment sector relies on movies. Each year, film industries generate billions of dollars in total earnings (McIntock, 2012). Presently, movies are a common kind of mass communication. Even Our everyday routine may be slightly impacted by television. They have an influence on how people dress, what individuals eat, and how they communicate (Ferla, 2010). Several studies (for example, Roberts et al., 1999; Gerbner et al., 2002) have found that recent movies and television shows include greater violence and drug usage than they did in the past. These aforementioned studies and theories showed that the media is mostly responsible for the rising number of young people who suffer from substance use disorders. The

goal of film producers is not to persuade viewers; therefore, most of the time, films may not have any impact because viewers watch them just for amusement (Hilton, 2006). There could, however, be an unforeseen consequence. Occasionally actors' portrayals of characters from films have an impact on viewers. The way an actor is dressed, or acts has an effect on viewers, particularly younger audiences, who want to imitate it in everyday life. Additionally, studies back up the idea that watching films affects viewers' cognitive processes. The information related to this investigation was gathered and analysed using quantitative approaches.

Data from various research on this subject have been analysed, and the results show that films have a definite impact on young people (Hanewinkel et al., 2008). Theorists of social cognition and persuasion confirm that viewers are most probably influenced by movies (Shapiro, 2002). This suggests that it is likely that watching films with actors who use illicit substances excessively will encourage youngsters to engage in unhealthy habits. Once these youngsters begin at an early age, it is quite difficult to eradicate these addictions (Hunt et al., 2011).

The quantitative research method of a questionnaire has been chosen to investigate the responses to the research questions. A Google form has been made, and information has been shared about it with friends, acquaintances, classmates, and organisations that help undergraduate students with their studies (these aforementioned groups were mostly assessed through Facebook). While analysing their responses, the reader could find out their general opinion on how the media sensitise individuals from the age of 18 to 25 against the adverse effect of cannabis. They were more likely to believe what Roberts et al. (1999) and Gerbner & Ozyegin (1997) suggested that in the past years, the representation of youngsters using cannabis and dealing with the substance on television has increased. Moreover, participants also agreed with a significant percentage (71%) that representing cannabis usage in movies and serials definitely influences the viewers to try the illicit substance. Although interestingly, the question asking whether they think cannabis usage in the media has a negative impact on their generation was one of the most divisive questions in the survey. Besides this question, there was another which had a fascinating result. Participants were asked if they believed that they were aware of the harmful effect of drugs. However, more individuals marked that they agree, Wurcel et al. (2015) highlighted in their research that people only generally recognize the adverse effects, but they do not have profound knowledge regarding substances. The project questionnaire has some limitations. The data gathered may not be generalizable to the entire population because there were only 62 participants, and the respondents were primarily close acquaintances who lived in one specific country. Different cultures and social systems may differ significantly from one another. The majority of the

respondents are more likely to share identical opinions and perspectives on this topic of study because they all reside in a similar environment. Because the drug is prohibited in many locations, the use of illicit narcotics varies greatly among cultures and nations, making it challenging to get reliable information.

Using and dealing with illicit substances like cannabis is an ongoing issue in almost every country in the world (Adams & Martin, 1996), and technical improvements in the media are prominently worsening the situation as they portray substance use improperly (Hasantha et al., 2005). Media has a potent influence on how individuals behave, think, and perceive things and also on how they use information (Ferla, 2020). According to many research (Caballero, 2023; Fernandez-Collado, 1978; Hunt et al., 2011), young individuals from the age of 18-25 are the most exposed generation to illicit drug incidents. The reason behind it might be that they constantly desire to fit into their friend group, as they are scared of being stigmatised (Hunt et al., 2011). What could be the solution to this ongoing issue? Hanewinkel et al. (2008) study suggests that if parents and guardians paid more attention to their children's television-using habits, it would reduce the chance of youngsters trying cannabis and becoming addicts in the future. Young people need to be made aware of the detrimental effects of cannabis on their physical and mental health (Hasin, 2005). Making decisions regarding their drug usage can be aided by educating them on the short- and long-term adverse effects of cannabis. Programmes for drug education in schools, community outreach initiatives, and social media campaigns can all deliver this education (Hasin, 2005). Young people who use cannabis at risk frequently fail to receive the social support they need from their families, peers, and community (Gulliver & Fowler, 2022). Providing social support can aid in preventing teen cannabis use (Wills & Cleary, 1996). Parents can play a significant part in providing social support by encouraging healthy lives and developing solid relationships with their kids (Wills & Cleary, 1996). Additionally, community-based initiatives that offer young people excellent role models and include them in constructive pursuits can be successful in reducing cannabis use (Gulliver & Fowler, 2022).

All things taken into consideration, the project showed evidence of how the media sensitises young individuals about the adverse effect of cannabis usage. It also included theories and many publications that support this hypothesis. It has been discussed that the portrayal of cannabis-related themes in movies and series has a significantly powerful effect not just on the youth but on the majority of age groups. Besides these, the project mentioned some methods on how young individuals can be prevented from cannabis usage and what might help them in order to cope with this issue.

References

Adams, I.B. & Martin, B.R. (1996). *Cannabis: pharmacology and toxicology in animals and humans*. *Addiction*, 91, 1585-614.

Aust, Charles F. and Zillmann, Dolf (1996) 'Effects of Victim Exemplification in Television News on Viewer Perception of Social Issues', *Journalism and Mass Communication Quarterly* 73(4): 787–803.

Bandura A. (2001) *Social Cognitive Theory of Mass Communication*, *Media Psychology*, 3:3, 265-299, DOI: 10.1207/S1532785XMEP0303_03 (accessed:08/03/2023).

Bandura, A., Ross, D., & Ross, S. A. (1963). Imitation of film-mediated aggressive models. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 66(1), 3-11. doi: 10.1037/h0048687.

Brosius, H. (1996) 'The Influence of Case Reports on Recipients' Judgment', *Rundfunk und Fernsehen* 44(1): 51–69.

Caballero G. C., Torrejón-Guirado, MC., Caballero C., (2023) Adolescents and youths' opinions about the factors associated with cannabis use: a qualitative study based on the I-Change model. *BMC Nurs* 22, 114 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-023-01283-z> (accessed: 16/04/2023).

Castaldelli-Maia, J., Bhugra, D., de Andrade, A., & Lotufo-Neto, F. (2013). Substance Use and Misuse in Brazilian Movies (2000-2008). *Substance Use & Misuse*, 48(3), 248- 257.

Cin et.al, (2009), Watching and drinking: Expectancies, prototypes, and peer affiliations mediate the effect of exposure to alcohol use in movies on adolescent drinking, <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2746653/> (accessed: 08/08/2023).

Cohen, J. & Weimann, G. (2000). "Cultivation Revisited: Some Genres Have Some Effects on Some Viewers". *Communication Reports*, 13(2), 99.

Dewey, W.L. (1986). *Cannabinoid pharmacology*. *Pharmacological Reviews*, 38, 151-78.

European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction -(EMCDDA) https://www.emcdda.europa.eu/emcdda-home-page_en (accessed:19/03/2023).

Farber, D. (2021). *The War on Drugs: A History*. New York, USA: New York University Press. <https://doi-org.emu.londonmet.ac.uk/10.18574/nyu/9781479811397.001.0001> (accessed:03/03/2023).

Ferla, (2010), *Film and Fashion: Just Friends*

http://www.nytimes.com/2010/03/04/fashion/04COSTUME.html?pagewanted=all&_r=0
(accessed:03/03/2023).

Fernandez-Collado, C. F., Greenberg, B. S., Korzenny, F. and Atkin, C. K. (1978) 'Sexual Intimacy and Drug Use in TV Series', *Journal of Communication* 28(3): 31–37.

Gerbner, G., G., L., Morgan, M., Signorielli, N., & Jackson-Beeck, M. (1979). "The Demonstration of Power: Violence Profile No. 10". *Journal of Communication*, 29, 177- 196.

Grube, (2004), *Alcohol in the Media: Drinking Portrayals, Alcohol Advertising, and Alcohol Consumption Among Youth* <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK37586/> (accessed:03/03/2023).

Guglielmino, L.M., (2012) *International Journal of Self-Directed Learning* Volume 9, Number 1, Spring

Gulliver, T.L., Fowler, K. (2022) Exploring Social Context and Psychological Distress in Adult Canadians with Cannabis Use Disorder: To What Extent Do Social Isolation and Negative Relationships Predict Mental Health?. *Psychiatr Q* 93, 311–323 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11126-021-09950-7> (accessed:18/04/2023).

Hanewinkel, R., Morgenstern, M., Tanski, S. E., & Sargent, J. D. (2008). Longitudinal study of parental movie restriction on teen smoking and drinking in Germany. *Addiction*, 103(10), 1722-1730. doi:10.1111/j.1360-0443.2008.02308.x (accessed:19/03/2023).

Hasantha G., Chapman, S. and Campbell, S. (2005) 'Sex and Drugs in Popular Movies: An Analysis of the Top 200 Films', *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine* 98(10): 464–70.

Hellum, M. (2010) 'Performing cannabis in the light of the backpacker discourse', *Contemporary Drug Problems*, 37(1), pp. 165–187. doi:10.1177/009145091003700108. (accessed:19/03/2023).

Hilton, (2006), *Subliminal messages in films and their potential effects on ESP*.

http://ufdcimages.uflib.ufl.edu/UF/E0/01/34/07/00001/hilton_j.pdf (accessed:09/09/2023).

Hunt, K., S., H., Sargent, J., Lewars, H., Young, R., & West, P. (2011). Is there an association between seeing incidents of alcohol or drug use in films and young Scottish adults' own alcohol or drug use? A cross sectional study. *BMC Public Health*, 11(1), 259- 269. doi:10.1186/1471-2458-11-259 (Accessed:10/03/2023).

Ju I., Rho E., Hinsley A. (2022) Poly Social Media Use: Roles of Informational Norms and Emotion Regulation. *Journal of Health Communication* 27:11-12, pages 812-824.

Kokotovič KO, Pšunder M, Kirbiš A. (2022) Cannabis Use and Parenting Practices among Young People: The Impact of Parenting Styles, Parental Cannabis-Specific Rules, and Parental Cannabis Use. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19138080> (accessed:16/04/2023).

Lalander, P. (2001.) *Hela världen är din—en bok om unga heroinister*[Hooked on Heroin]. Lund, Sweden: Studentlitteratur.

Lindholm O. F., How media affects youth, TedxHow the media affects youth | Oda Faremo Lindholm | TEDxOslo (Accessed:10/11/2022).

Leyens J-P, Camino L, Parke R, Berkowitz L. (1975). *Effects of movie violence on aggression in a field setting as a function of group dominance and cohesion*. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1977-03582-001> (accessed: 03/08/2023).

Long, J. A., O'Connor, Patrick G., Gerbner, George and Concato, John (2002) 'Use of Alcohol, Illicit Drugs, and Tobacco Among Characters on Prime-time Television', in *Substance Abuse* 23(2): 95–103.

Martin, B.R. (1986). Cellular effects of cannabinoids. *Pharmacological Reviews*,38, 45-74.

McIntock, (2012), Global Box Office Hit \$32.6 Bil in 2011, Fueled by Exploding International Growth. <http://www.hollywoodreporter.com/news/global-box-office-chinainternational-growth-326-303324> (accessed:03/03/2023).

Merchant, Z. F., (2013) "A study on the depiction of drug usage, alcohol consumption and cigarette smoking in movies and its perceived effect on a young audience. A comparative study of American and Indian cinema and their respective Audiences." *Graduate Theses and Dissertations*. <http://scholarcommons.usf.edu/etd/4826> (accessed: 08/03/2023).

Nabi R. L., Clark S.,(2008) Exploring the Limits of Social Cognitive Theory: Why Negatively Reinforced Behaviors on TV May Be Modeled Anyway, *Journal of Communication*, Volume 58, Issue 3, September 2008, Pages 407–427, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2008.00392.x> (accessed:22/03/2023).

Newcomb, M. D., & Bentler, P. M. (1989). Substance use and abuse among children and teenagers. *American Psychologist*, 44(2), 242–248. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.44.2.242> (accessed:15/04/2023).

O'Loughlin J. L., Dugas E. L., O'Loughlin E. K., Winickoff J. P., Montreuil A., Wellman R. J., Sylvestre M. P., Hanusaik N.,(2019) Parental Cannabis Use Is Associated with Cannabis Initiation and Use in Offspring, *The Journal of Pediatrics*, Volume 206, Pages 142-147.e1, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2018.10.057>. (accessed: 16/04/2023).

Parker, H., Williams, L., & Aldridge, J. (2002). *The Normalization of 'Sensible' Recreational Drug Use: Further Evidence from the North West England Longitudinal Study*. *Sociology*, 36(4), 941–964. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003803850203600408> (accessed: 15/04/2023).

Praditomo, M.A.A. et al. (2022) 'Personal Chatbot Evaluation with Elaboration Likelihood Model on Social Messaging Application', 2022 10th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT), Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT), 2022 10th International Conference on, pp. 211–216. doi:10.1109/ICoICT55009.2022.9914832.

Petty, R E., and John C. (1986). *The Elaboration Likelihood Method of Persuasion* . New York: Academic Press. Print.

Roberts, D. F., Foehr, U. G., Rideout, V. J. and Brodie, M. (1999) *Kids and Media at the New Millennium*. Menlo Park, CA: The Henry J. Kaiser Family Foundation.

Room, R. (2015). Portraying the alcoholic: Images of intoxication and addiction in American alcoholism movies, 1931–1962. *Substance Use & Misuse*, 50(4), 503–507.

Schroder, H. M., Driver, M. J. and Streufert S. (1967) *Human Information Processing*. New York: Holt Rinehart and Winston.

Selvaggi G, Spagnolo A. G., Elander A. (2017) A review of illicit psychoactive drug use in elective surgery patients: Detection, effects, and policy, *International Journal of Surgery*, Volume 48, Pages 160-165, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2017.10.074>. (accessed: 16/04/2023).

Shapiro, H. (2002). From Chaplin to Charlie—cocaine, Hollywood and the movies. *Drugs: Education, Prevention & Policy*, 9(2), 133-141. doi:10.1080/09687630110119161 (accessed:08/03/2023).

Shrum, L. J. (2001) 'Processing Strategy Moderates the Cultivation Effect', *Human Communication Research* 27(1): 94–120.

Sridharan M. (2021) Think Insights June 8, 2021 *Elaboration Likelihood Model Persuasion Theory*, <<https://thinkinsights.net/leadership/elaboration-likelihood-model/>> (Accessed: 22/03/2023).

Sotirovic, M. (2001) 'Affective and Cognitive Processes as Mediators of Media Influences on Crime-policy Preferences', *Mass Communication and Society* 4(3): 311–29.

Solowij, N. (1998). *Cannabis and cognitive functioning*. Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511526824> (accessed: 03/03/2023).

Sulkunen, P. (2002). Between culture and nature: Intoxication in cultural studies of alcohol and drug use., 29,253-276.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2021). World Drug Report 2021. Retrieved from <https://wdr.unodc.org/wdr2021/> (accessed:15/04/2023).

Wills, T. A., & Cleary, S. D. (1996). How are social support effects mediated? A test with parental support and adolescent substance use. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 71(5), 937–952.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.71.5.937> (accessed: 18/04/2023).

Winick, C. and Winick, M.P. (1976) 'Drug Education and the Content of Mass Media Dealing with "Dangerous Drugs' and Alcohol", in Ron E. Ostman (ed.) *Communication Research and Drug Education*, pp. 11–15. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications.

Wong, 2012, 5 ways You Don't Realize Movies are Controlling your Brain, <http://www.cracked.com/blog/5-ways-you-dont-realize-movies-are-controlling-yourbrain/> (accessed:09/03/2023).

Wurcel A. G. , Merchant E. A., Clark P. R., Stone D.R., (2015) Emerging and Underrecognized Complications of Illicit Drug Use, *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, Volume 61, Issue 12, Pages 1840–1849,
<https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/civ689> (accessed: 16/04/2023).

Yadav, Poonam & Parajuli, Rejina. (2021). Knowledge Regarding Drug Abuse among School Students.
https://assets.researchsquare.com/files/rs-226710/v1_covered.pdf?c=1631854606 (Accessed:10/11/2022).